

SYNTHESIS OF NANO-SIZED PLATINUM BY POLYOL PROCESS

J. H. Lee¹, S. H. An¹, S. H. Kim¹, M. H. Lee² and Y. D. Kim^{1*}

¹Division of Materials Science and Engineering, Hanyang University, Seoul 133-791, Korea

²Production Technology R&D Division, Korea Institute of Industrial Technology, Incheon 406-840, Republic of Korea

* Corresponding author (ydkim1@hanyang.ac.kr)

Keywords: *Platinum, nano particle, polyol process, capping agent*

1 Introduction

Platinum (Pt) has been widely used such as catalyst of fuel cell[1] and exhausted gas clean system[2] due to high catalytic activity. However, the price of Pt is continuously increasing each year according to low-yield and diversity of application. So, it has been briskly proceeded to enhancing efficiency of catalytic properties by controlling the size[3] and the shape of particles[4] or developing alternative metal[5].

In this study, we synthesized Pt nano particle by using polyol process which is one of liquid chemical phase reduction method. Liquid chemical phase reduction has various merits. For example, synthesized process is simple and it is possible to control size and shape of particle by adding additive such as capping agent and metal salt.

H₂PtCl₆·6H₂O, used as a precursor, was dissolved in Ethylene glycol (EG), used as a reducing agent, and we synthesized Pt nano particle depending on temperature and time of synthesis. Also, we added polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) as capping agent for reducing the size and dispersed the particles. In addition, we used AgNO₃, as metal salt, to control shape of Pt particles.

2 Experimental procedures

To research effect of the quantity of PVP, as capping agent, One solution A was made of 0.04 mmol H₂PtCl₆·6H₂O as a precursor dissolved in 5 mL EG and the other solution B was made of 0, 40 and 80 mg PVP was dissolved in 20 mL EG. Then the solution B poured into the 3-neck flask and heated at 160°C. When the temperature was reached at 160°C, solution A was poured into the flask so two solution was mixed at 160°C with stirring at 300

rpm for minimize agglomeration. After 5 min, solution in flask was changed from yellow to dark brown.

Also, to control shape of Pt particles, solution A was made of 0.02 M AgNO₃ dissolved in 2.5 mL EG. B solution consisted of 0.0625 M H₂PtCl₆·6H₂O dissolved in EG. Finally, solution C was made of 0.735 M PVP dissolved in EG.

First, to synthesize Ag seed, solution A poured into the 3-neck flask and heated at 160°C for 30 min. Then, solution B and solution C dropwisely added in heated solution and mixed solution maintained for 60 min during synthesis.

After the synthesis for nano particle, the colloid solution was cooled at room temperature and washed by acetone and ethalnlol several times. To analyze Pt precipitations, we used scanning electron microscope (SEM), Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and Particle size analyzer (PSA) for the purpose of evaluating the size, shape and dispersibility of Pt nano particles.

3 Results and discussion

It is generally agreed that the size of metal nano particles is determined by the rate of reduction of the metal precursor. At high temperatures, ethylene glycol is decomposed to yield in situ reducing species, CH₃CHO, for the reduction of the metal ions to metallic particles [6]. The formation of Pt nano particles initiates from the following reactions in EG solution under heating mantle [7].

Fig. 1 shows XRD pattern of synthesized Pt particle with 80 mg PVP. XRD peak typically shows 39.6° , 46.1° , 67.2° platinum peak (JCPDF: 87-0642).

We made comparison of synthesized particles between with-PVP and without-PVP. Fig. 1 shows the TEM images and size distribution of Pt nano particle with-PVP and without-PVP. Fig. 2 a) shows agglomerated Pt particles that consist of ~ 10 - 20 nm sized Pt nano particles. An agglomerated Pt particle size is about $3.61 \mu\text{m}$. Fig. 2 b) shows Pt nano particles synthesized with 40 mg PVP. They seem to be so smaller than Fig. 2 a) but somewhat agglomerated. Average particle size of Pt Particles with 40 mg PVP is 46.66 nm . Finally, fig. 2 c) shows Pt nano particles synthesized with 80 mg PVP. They seem to be well dispersed and their size glow less and less. Average particle size of Pt Particles with 80 mg PVP is 16.37 nm (Fig. 2 f)).

PVP is well known as one of the dispersant. Carbonyl group of PVP tends to stick to metal ion or metal nuclei. Electronegativity of O(3.44) is larger than that of C(2.55). So C of carbonyl group relatively becomes δ^+ and O becomes δ^- [8]. Because of this, O of carbonyl group of PVP sticks to metal surface. In this process, PVP capped Pt nano particles and controlled their size.

Fig.3 shows average Pt particles size and standard deviation of synthesized platinum according to add concentration of PVP. As concentration of PVP is higher, It seems that average Pt particles size and standard deviation is smaller.

To control the shape of Pt, AgNO_3 is added as a metal salt. Fig. 4 shows TEM image of shape controlled cubic type Pt nano particle.

Pt has face centered cubic(fcc) structure and surround eight (111) planes and six (100) planes. fcc structure metal generally has surface energy in order of orientation; $(110) > (100) > (111)$ [9]. It is possible to describe broken bonding. The number of broken bonding in fcc structure is (111)-3, (100)-4, and (110)-5. In case of Pt, it is confirmed that surface energy in order of orientation like $(110) > (100) > (111)$ [10].

It is known that silver prefers (100) to (111)[11], and Strüber et al.[12] confirm that desorption energy of silver stucked to (100) of Pt is larger than that of silver stucked to (111) of Pt.

Fig. 5 shows XRD pattern of controlled cubic type Pt by Ag seed. It shows not only Pt but also silver peak.

Fig. 1. XRD pattern of synthesized platinum particle with 80 mg PVP.

Fig. 2. TEM micrographs of synthesized Pt nano particles with various concentration of PVP; a) 0 mg, b) 40 mg, and c) 80 mg. And size distribution of Pt nano particle with various concentration of PVP; d) 0 mg, e) 40 mg, and f) 80 mg.

Fig. 3. Average particle sizes and standard deviations of synthesized platinum according to add concentration of PVP.

Fig. 4. TEM images of synthesized platinum nano particles adding AgNO_3 (0.02 M) for 30 min pre-heating times and 60 min post-heating time at 160°C .

Fig. 5. XRD pattern of shape controlled platinum particle by AgNO_3 , as metal salt.

4 Summary

We synthesized Pt nano particle by using polyol process added 0, 40 and 80 mg PVP and each synthesized particle size was about 3.61 μm , 45.66 nm and 16.37 nm. It was shown that particles were agglomerated and formed thick and round type chunks without-PVP. Also, the more amount of PVP as a capping agent is added, the smaller Pt nano particle we had. Therefore, this is shown that PVP had an effect on particle size during synthesized chemical reaction time. Also, AgNO_3 used as metal salt is added for shape control of platinum and we synthesize cubic type Pt nano particles.

References

- [1] X. Teng, X. Liang, S. Maksimuk, and H. Yang, "Synthesis of Porous Pt Nanoparticles", *small*, Vol. 2, No. 2, pp 249-253, 2006.
- [2] J. Ren and R. D. Tilley "Shape-Controlled Growth of Pt Nanoparticles". *small*, Vol. 3, No. 9, pp 1508-1512, 2007.
- [3] T. Teranishi, M. Hosoe, T. Tanaka, and M. Miyake "Size Control of Monodispersed Pt Nanoparticles and Their 2D Organization by Electrophoretic Deposition". *J. Phys. Chem.*, Vol. 103, No. 19, pp 3818-3827, 1999.
- [4] Z. Peng, and H. Yang "Designer Pt nanoparticle: Control of shape, composition in alloy, nanostructure and electrocatalytic property", Vol. 4, pp 143-164 Publisher, 2001.
- [5] S. Alayoglu, A. Nilekar, M. Mavrikakis, and B. Eichhorn, "Ru-Pt core-shell nanoparticles for preferential oxidation of carbon monoxide in hydrogen", Vol. 7, pp 333-338, 2008.

- [6] S. Komarneni, D.S. Li, B. Newalkar, H. Katsuki, and A.S.Bhalla, A.S., "Microwave-polyol process for Pt and Ag nanoparticles", *Langmuir*, Vol. 18, pp 5959-5962, 2002..
- [7] M. Tsuji, M. Hashimoto, Y. Nishizawa, M. Kubokawa, and T. Tsuji, "Microwave-assisted synthesis of metallic nanostructures in solution", *Chem. Eur. J.*, Vol.11, pp 440-452, 2005.
- [8] H. J. Lee, *News & Information for Chemical Engineers*, Vol. 26 pp 715-721, 2008.
- [9] D. A. Porter, K. E. Eastering, and M. Y. Sherif, "Phase Transformations in Metals and Alloys", 3rd edition, pp.113, 2009.
- [10] T. K. Galeev, N. N. Bulgakov, G. A. Savelieva and N. M. Popova, *React. Kinet. Catal. Lett.*, Vol. 14, pp 61-65, 1980.
- [11] H. Song, F. Kim, S. Connor, G. A. Somorjai, and P. Yang, *J. Phys. Chem. B*, Vol. 109 pp 188-192, 2005.
- [12] U. Strüber Strüber, A. Kastner and J. Küppers, *Thin Solid Films*, Vol. 250 pp 101-108, 1994.